

The Analysis of Teacher Talk in "Learner-centered" Teaching Mode

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Abstract : Being main teaching media and major source of comprehensive target language input, teacher talk plays an important role in learners' second-language acquisition. Under the trend of "learner-centered" teaching mode, some researchers think that the best teacher talk means less. But the author holds that, in Chinese second language classroom, it is not advisable to lay too much stress on the formal students' participation, which requires the teacher to say as little as possible and the student to say as much as possible. The emphasis should be put in how to raise teacher talk's quality.

Keywords : Comprehensive language input, "learner-centered" teaching mode, teacher talk, teacher talk's quality.

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